

COMPETENCE APPROACH IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekistonda maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ingliz tilini o‘rgatishda yanada samaraliroq, zamonaviy yondashuvdan foydalanish ko‘rib chiqiladi. So‘nggi yillarda barcha mamlakatlarda yosh bolalarga chet tilini o‘rgatish tobora keng tarqalgan. Erta yoshda ingliz tilini o‘rganish tendentsiyasi uch yoshdan boshlab tilni turli shakl va sharoitlarda o‘rgana oladigan maktabgacha ta’lim muassasalaridagi o‘quvchilar uchun mos uslubga ehtiyoj tug‘dirdi. O‘zbekistonda chet tillarini o‘rgatish maktabgacha ta’limning ajralmas qismiga aylanar ekan, bolalarning samarali bilim olish imkoniyatiga ega bo‘lishi juda muhim.

Kalit so‘zlar: maktabgacha ta’lim, yosh o‘quvchilar, erta bolalik ta’limi, ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o‘rgatish, kompetensiya yondashuvi.

Аннотация. Данная статья рассматривает использование более эффективного, современного подхода в преподавании английского языка детям дошкольного возраста в Узбекистане. В последние годы преподавание иностранного языка детям раннего возраста становится все более распространенным явлением во всех странах. Эта тенденция к изучению EFL в более раннем возрасте создала потребность в методе, подходящем для молодых учеников, которые могут изучать язык в различных формах и условиях, начиная с трехлетнего возраста. Поскольку обучение иностранным языкам становится неотъемлемой частью дошкольного образования в Узбекистане, очень важно, чтобы дети имели возможность учиться в эффективной форме.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное обучение, учащиеся младшего возраста, обучение английскому языку как иностранному, компетентностный подход.

Abstract. This paper is an attempt to promote the use of a more effective, modern approach in teaching English to young learners in Uzbekistan. Teaching a foreign language to young learners has become an increasingly common phenomenon across borders in recent years. This trend towards EFL learning at a younger age has created a need for a method that is suitable for young learners, who can learn language in a variety of ways and settings from the age of 3 years onwards. As foreign language instruction becomes an integral part of preschool education in Uzbekistan, it is crucial that children are given the opportunity to learn in an enjoyable and effective manner.

Keywords: preschool, young learners, early childhood education, teaching English as foreign language, competence approach.

Tremendous changes in the mental and physical development of children in recent years have led to great advances in the understanding of how children learn. Refined methods have been designed to achieve optimum results in EFL learning for children. Foreign language study has been shown to contribute to children's mental development, flexibility in thinking and reasoning and the understanding of their mother tongue, in addition to preparing children to communicate with speakers of other languages (Nikolov 2016). Children now are in need of a special pedagogy that best suits their learning ability and which above all provides them with authentic experiences in order to facilitate the learning process.

Competence approach has become one of the most important ideas in the field of language teaching in the last two decades. It is a response to dissatisfaction with both the results of teaching and the processes by which these results are achieved. Competence in a language is clearly a complex matter. The learners need to know how to do things with language as well as know about the language. Knowing about the language includes knowing its forms and structures (grammatical competence), knowing about how the language is used in particular situations (sociolinguistic competence), understanding what is meant in an utterance, even if it is not explicitly stated (pragmatic competence), and knowing how language is used to construe and understand the world in the mind (psycholinguistic competence). Learners also need to develop skills in using the language. These are the four traditional skills of speaking, writing, reading and listening, but a more detailed analysis of language use identifies many subskills such as scanning a text, asking for clarification, or making a narrative. At any one time, a learner will want to learn a language in order to do a particular thing, for example take an academic course, read a novel, travel, conduct an international business negotiation, or make friends with speakers of the language and the language requirements for these activities will differ. The various forms of language use and their associated skills are generally referred to as performance. It is too simplistic to identify competence with knowledge about the language and performance with using the language, since using a language to do something always involves knowing and doing specific things with the language. But a useful distinction can be made between general knowledge about and skills in using a language, which can be applied to a wide range of language use activities, and specific knowledge and skills which are tied to particular activities.

The competence-based approach has been getting attention in all aspects of education, including foreign language teaching, in recent years. This is probably due to the fact that this approach offers a new perspective to a curriculum. While there are many definitions of what competence is, it is generally known as the ability to do something. In the education sector, competence is the ability to master specific content in order to achieve certain goals. This may involve acquiring knowledge, mastering a certain skill, or producing something that is considered a standard. A competent person is able to do a task to a level of proficiency, and the end goal of education is to produce competent people. This means that the focus in education is shifting from an education-centered approach to a student-centered approach. In defining what competence is in a foreign language, it is useful to refer to the Common European Framework of Reference for languages (CEFR), which has clearly defined levels of proficiency in language learning. This document outlines what learners are expected to do at an indicative level of learning. It also separates language skills and competencies into different categories. By using the CEFR, teachers are able to assess learning progress relative to the level of proficiency that one is attempting to achieve. This contrasts with older syllabuses that usually only measure progress by an arbitrary increase in test scores. As it is possible to assess what level a student is at and what level they are trying to achieve, the CEFR provides a clear focus for learners to progress to higher levels of language mastery. This, in turn, facilitates more efficient teaching and learning towards clear objectives.

The competence approach to teaching English to young learners is based on the belief that the primary function of language learning is for learners to be able to interact with others in a given community of practice (e.g., the EFL classroom) in ways that allow them to participate in the practices understood as 'the use of language' within that community. From this perspective, competence in a foreign language is best measured by the ability of a speaker to perform language

tasks in the real world. This principle provides the theoretical foundation for the syllabus. The pedagogical implications drawn from this basic principle are that language learning tasks in the classroom should represent, as closely as possible, the kinds of uses to which the language will be put outside the classroom, and that the primary criterion for a successful lesson is that the children were able to do the task. To put it another way, if the aim is for the children to learn to say and understand certain things in English, then a reasonable test for whether or not they have learned what has been taught is whether or not they can say those things and understand them when they hear others say them.

Designing authentic learning tasks to meet identified learning objectives is of paramount importance in applying the competence approach. It is a task-based, learner-centered pedagogy that focuses on the significance of learners' active engagement. It requires teachers to develop a deep understanding of what a task involves and entails. Furthermore, the use of something called "realia" is quite common in language classrooms especially, in preschool classrooms when children learn by touching objects while naming them. By bringing in an object from real life—whether it is play kitchen utensils, foreign currency, or traffic signs—and using it to demonstrate a vocabulary word or participate in some kind of charades, this can be similar to board games and show how the language being learned can be used in real-life situations. The use of realia is good to help learners understand and grasp onto a concept, or for more concrete learners—to learn specific vocabulary. An extension from this might be to make a sorting activity using the realia to foster some higher-level thinking. For example, the teacher could scatter various sports balls and sports equipment on a table, and the learners would have to sort them into the different sports they belong to—an activity that is both simple and a simulation of a real-life event. Teachers are likely to come across trendy terms and strategies in education. But since the Competence Approach is essentially a call for the use of common sense, doing what is practical and what makes the most sense, it is much more agreeable with parents, teachers, and students than past educational paradigms. So, the implementation of Competence Approach strategies is often favored and welcomed. By including real-life simulations, a teacher can show small children the importance of a lesson and provide a strong motivation for the kids. There is a great diversity of activities that one can use to simulate real-life events. For example, the use of board games can be useful. Language teachers frequently employ games to help learners practice the language in a non-threatening setting. Although many games are just for fun, board games can be an active strategy to work on language forms and functions. At times, they can be used as evaluation tools to see what learners have learned in a non-threatening environment. Another strategy in competence approach to teaching English to preschool learners in Uzbekistan would be collaborative learning. Collaborative learning is an important component of the competence approach, as it provides a forum for learners to integrate several language skills in the process of completing a task in a group, usually required of them to negotiate meaning and work towards achieving a common goal (O'Donnell, 2013). Collaborative learning tasks can be as simple as pair work when young learners could sort out fruit and vegetables, or more complex problem-based learning scenarios with elder preschool children. The goal of promoting collaborative learning in the EFL classroom is to provide realistic language use situations where students take control of their own language learning and are motivated to develop language skills to a level that allows them to be successful in completion of the task. The five learning conditions of collaborative learning as defined by Barkley, Cross and Major (2014) are: positive interdependence, individual and group accountability, promotive interaction, social skills, and group processing. These five learning

conditions help to steer the students toward completion of their groups' task and ensure they remain on-track. The conditions are essential as they provide scaffolding that aids the development of students' learning skills at any age and specifically at an early age.

A competence approach implies that learners have passed through a series of levels or stages. Each level comprises a body of knowledge and a set of skills, attitudes, and social competence which are required to function effectively at that level. Learners are considered to be competent in a foreign language when they can perform language tasks in a 'real world' context and can demonstrate the set of competencies which are required to carry out these tasks. This presents further challenges. Young children are still in the process of acquiring many of these competencies in their native language or have not yet fully developed them. The teacher must make decisions concerning the extent to which he should work on the content of tasks so that the child can progress in his overall cognitive development or solely on the language task itself. An example of the latter would be a child who has difficulty in solving a problem in his own language but understands when it is presented to him by the teacher in the foreign language. The ideal is to work on both, but this may not always be possible, and a balance must be struck. In such cases, the child might benefit from a task which is below his current cognitive level if it helps him to develop much-needed cognitive and problem-solving skills. This is often the case with children of expatriate families who attend local schools in the foreign language.

The teacher must also take into account the target situation where the child will use this language. The range of tasks and competencies is broader than for adults. Effective strategies and awareness of register and sociocultural constraints are competencies that require a great deal of practice for mastery. This level of depth in language learning is often beyond the competence of the child language learner, but nonetheless, it provides a framework for progression in foreign language learning right up to adulthood.

In the context of young learners in teaching English, addressing individual needs often relate to the pace of learning and degree of support. Kusuma-Powell (2009) maintains that individuals have different rates of brain maturation, so it is normal for young students to be at different cognitive developmental stages. A balance must be struck between providing sufficient cognitive challenge and minimizing failure for those students who may struggle to transfer basic literacy skills from their first language to English. Withdrawing students from mainstream L1 and L2 classes for additional literacy support is unlikely to be advocating their best interests, since the cognitive and affective benefits of bilingualism can only be attained through full participation in a second language community (Gibbons, 2002). The provision of mother-tongue support within a competence-based EFL program is another method of preventing students from becoming disengaged due to the double challenge of learning academic content through a foreign language.

The competence approach in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teaching to very young learners in preschools emphasizes the development of a broad range of language competencies, skills, and abilities rather than solely focusing on linguistic knowledge. This approach recognizes that language learning involves more than just mastering vocabulary and grammar; it also involves the acquisition of communicative, social, cultural, and cognitive competencies that enable learners to use English effectively in various contexts. Here are several key aspects of the competence approach in EFL teaching to very young learners in preschools:

Holistic Development: The competence approach recognizes that language learning is part of a broader process of holistic development that encompasses cognitive, social, emotional, and physical aspects. EFL teaching in preschools aims to foster the overall development of children by

integrating language learning with other areas of learning and development, such as play, exploration, and interaction.

Communicative Competence: Central to the competence approach is the development of communicative competence, which involves the ability to use language effectively to communicate meaning, express ideas, and interact with others. EFL teaching in preschools focuses on providing opportunities for children to engage in meaningful communication through activities such as storytelling, role-play, and group discussions.

Contextualized Learning: The competence approach emphasizes the importance of contextualized learning, where language is taught and learned in meaningful, real-life contexts that are relevant to children's interests, experiences, and everyday lives. EFL teaching in preschools integrates language learning with activities and experiences that are culturally and developmentally appropriate for young learners.

Task-Based Learning: Task-based learning is a key pedagogical approach associated with the competence approach in EFL teaching. Instead of focusing solely on language forms and structures, task-based learning emphasizes the completion of meaningful tasks that require the use of language for real purposes. In preschool EFL teaching, tasks may involve activities such as games, songs, crafts, and storytelling that engage children in active, hands-on learning experiences.

Assessment for Learning: The competence approach advocates for assessment practices that focus on assessing learners' progress in developing language competencies and skills rather than simply testing their knowledge of grammar and vocabulary. Assessment in preschool EFL teaching is often formative and ongoing, providing feedback to teachers and learners to support ongoing learning and development.

Inclusive and Child-Centered Approach: The competence approach in EFL teaching to very young learners emphasizes an inclusive and child-centered approach that recognizes and respects the individual differences, interests, and needs of each child. EFL teaching in preschools aims to create a supportive and nurturing learning environment where all children feel valued, empowered, and motivated to learn.

Overall, the competence approach in EFL teaching to very young learners in preschools emphasizes the holistic development of children's language competencies and skills within meaningful, contextually rich learning experiences. By integrating language learning with other areas of learning and development and adopting child-centered pedagogical approaches, preschool EFL teaching can effectively support the early language development and overall growth of young learners.

REFERENCES

1. O'Donnell, A. M., & Hmelo-Silver, C. E. (2013). Introduction: What is collaborative learning?: An overview. *The international handbook of collaborative learning*, 1-15.
2. Kusuma-Powell, O. (2004). Multi-lingual, but not making it in international schools. *Journal of Research in International Education*, 3(2), 157-172.
3. Nikolov, M. (Ed.). (2016). *Assessing young learners of English: Global and local perspectives* (pp. 1-18). New York, NY: Springer.
4. Barkley, E. F., Major, C. H., & Cross, K. P. (2014). *Collaborative learning techniques: A handbook for college faculty*. John Wiley & Sons.